

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Vegetal polyphenol extracts as antioxidants for the stabilization of PLA: towards fully bio-based polymers formulation

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LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY-MASS SPECTROMETRY (LC-MS) ANALYSIS OF VEGETAL EXTRACTS

Figure S1. LC-MS chromatogram in negative mode of ethanol/water extracts of green tea residues.

Figure S2. LC-MS chromatogram in negative mode of ethanol/water extracts of grape marc.

Figure S3. LC-MS chromatogram in negative mode of ethanol/water extracts of bramble leaves.

Figure S4. LC-MS chromatogram in negative mode of ethanol/water extracts yellow onion peels.

Figure S5. LC-MS chromatogram in negative mode of ethanol/water extracts of pomegranate peels.

Table S1. Polyphenols and other compounds identified in the vegetal extracts by LC-MS.

N°	Rt (min)	Compound	Chemical formula	M-H _{exp} (m/z)	MS ² fragment	Species					Reference
						GT C. sin	GM V. vin	BL R. sp	YO A. cep	PG P. gra	
1	3,68	Tartaric acid	C ₄ H ₆ O ₆	149,0075	87/72/59		o				Standard
2	3,87	Quinic acid	C ₇ H ₁₂ O ₆	191,0561	191/85/127/93/87	o		o			Standard
3	4,39	Saccharose	C ₁₂ H ₂₂ O ₁₁	341,1084	89/59/341/179/71	o	o	o	o	o	Standard
4	7,25	Citric acid	C ₆ H ₈ O ₇	191,0186	111/87/85/191/129	o		o		o	Standard
5	7,71	Galloyl-hexoside	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₁₀	331,0670	331/169/151/271/211	o				o	1,2
6	8,58	Theogallin	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₁₀	343,0666	169/343/173/125/191	o					Standard
7	8,64	Gallic acid	C ₇ H ₆ O ₅	169,0132	125/169/126/97/81	o	o	o		o	Standard
8	8,89	Protocatechuic acid-O-hexoside	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₉	315,0719	153/109/154/315/109				o		3
9	10,45	Gallocatechin	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₇	305,0665	125/305/167/179/165	o				o	Standard
10	10,47	Protocatechuic acid	C ₇ H ₆ O ₄	153,018	109/153/110/108/154		o		o		Standard
11	10,93	Punicalagin isomer	C ₄₈ H ₂₈ O ₃₀	1083,059	301/299/271/601/575					o	4
12	11,51	Neochlorogenic acid	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₉	353,0874	191/179/135/353/192			o			Standard
13	11,60	Protocatechuic acid isomer	C ₇ H ₆ O ₄	153,018	109/153/110/108/154				o		Standard
14	11,85	Punicalagin isomer	C ₄₈ H ₂₈ O ₃₀	1083,059	301/299/271/601/245					o	4
15	11,86	Procyanidin B1	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ O ₁₂	577,1424	289/125/407/425/161		o				Standard
16	11,88	Caffeoyl hexoside isomer	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ O ₉	341,0872	161/341/179/133/135			o			1
17	12,14	Epigallocatechin	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₇	305,0667	305/125/167/165/179	o					Standard
18	12,30	Caffeoyl hexoside isomer	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ O ₉	341,0871	179/281/161/135/221			o			1
19	12,65	Procyanidin B3	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ O ₁₂	577,1353	125/289/407/161/425		o				Standard
20	12,81	Caffeoyl hexoside isomer	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ O ₉	341,0872	179/281/161/251/135			o			1
21	13,27	Catechin	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₆	289,0717	289/245/109/125/203	o	o			o	Standard
22	13,34	Chlorogenic acid	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₉	353,0874	191/192/85/353/161			o			Standard
23	13,59	Procyanidin B2	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ O ₁₂	577,1351	289/125/407/425/161		o				Standard
24	14,42	Epigallocatechin gallate	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₁₈	457,0776	169/125/305/161/457	o					Standard
25	14,44	Sanguin H-6	C ₈₂ H ₅₄ O ₅₂	934,0729	301/315/275/633/229			o			Standard
26	14,56	Epicatechin	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₆	289,0714	289/245/109/125/203	o	o	o			Standard

GT C. sin: green tea residues (*Camellia sinensis*); GM V. vin: grape marc (*Vitis vinifera* var. *Gamay / Pinot Noir*); BL R. sp: bramble leaves (*Rubus* sp.); YO A. cep: yellow onion peels (*Allium cepa*); PG P. gra: pomegranate peels (*Punica granatum*) ; o : presence of the compound in the extract.

Table S1. Polyphenols and other compounds identified in the vegetal extracts by LC-MS. (continuation)

N°	Rt (min)	Compound	Chemical formula	M-H _{exp} (m/z)	MS ² fragment	Species					Reference
						GT C. sin	GM V. vin	BL R. sp	YO A. cep	PG P. gra	
27	14,68	Epigallocatechin gallate isomer	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₁₁	457,0771	169/125/305/161/457	o					Standard
28	15,02	Feruloyl glucose	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₉	355,1031	355/161/179/135/193			o			1
29	15,07	Epigallocatechin gallate isomer	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₁₁	457,0771	169/125/305/161/457	o					Standard
30	15,59	Ellagic acid pentoside isomer	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₁₂	433,0409	301/300/433/272/228			o			1
31	15,71	Myricetin-3-O-glucoside	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₁₃	479,0828	316/479/271/317/287	o					Standard
32	15,95	Unknown	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₈	317,0297	163/109/191/179/151				o		Not applicable
33	16,24	Ellagic acid pentoside isomer	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₁₂	433,0409	300/301/433/272/228			o			1
34	16,31	Ellagic acid-deoxyhexoside	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₁₁	447,0565	300/447/301/448/175					o	1,2
35	17,10	Quercetin-3-O-rutinoside	C ₂₇ H ₃₀ O ₁₆	609,1461	300/609/301/271/255	o					Standard
36	17,29	Epigallocatechin methyl gallate	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₁₁	471,0928	125/183/161/305/168	o					5
37	17,79	Apigenin-8-C-glucoside	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₁₀	431,0981	311/431/283/341/323	o					Standard
38	17,99	Ellagic acid	C ₁₄ H ₆ O ₈	300,9987	302/229/284/300/257			o		o	Standard
39	18,32	Quercetin-3-O-glucoside	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₁₂	463,0883	300/463/301/271/255	o					Standard
40	18,85	Quercetin-3-O-glucuronide	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₁₃	477,0668	301/447/151/179/255			o			Standard
41	18,93	Epicatechin gallate isomer	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₁₀	441,0821	169/289/125/441/245	o					Standard
42	20,17	Kaempferol 3-O-rutinoside	C ₂₇ H ₃₀ O ₁₅	593,1513	285/593/284/255/227	o					Standard
43	20,99	Kaempferol-3-O-galactoside	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₁₁	447,0933	447/284/255/285/227	o					Standard
44	22,25	Kaempferol-3-O-glucoside	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₁₁	447,0931	447/284/255/285/227	o					Standard
45	22,58	Kaempferol-3-O-glucuronide	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₁₂	461,0724	285/113/461/229/175			o			Standard
46	23,81	Epicatechin methyl gallate	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₁₀	455,0984	289/183/168/125/245	o					6
47	24,07	Quercetin-4'-O-glucoside	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₁₂	463,0877	301/151/179/300/463				o		Standard
48	25,58	Dimethoxy-kaempferol	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₉	363,0717	271/345/300/151/179				o		7
49	39,20	Quercetin	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	301,0349	301/151/179/121/107				o		Standard
50	40,53	Kaempferol	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	285,0402	285/151/229/185/257				o		Standard
51	40,73	Isorahmnetin	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₇	315,0507	315/300/151/316/301				o		Standard

GT C. sin: green tea residues (*Camellia sinensis*); GM V. vin: grape marc (*Vitis vinifera* var. *Gamay / Pinot Noir*); BL R. sp: bramble leaves (*Rubus* sp.); YO A. cep: yellow onion peels (*Allium cepa*); PG P. gra: pomegranate peels (*Punica granatum*) ; o : presence of the compound in the extract.

THERMOGRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS OF ADDITIVES

Figure S6. TG/DTG curves of Irganox 1010 at 10 °C/min in a nitrogen atmosphere.

Figure S7. TG/DTG curves of green tea residues at 10 °C/min in a nitrogen atmosphere.

Figure S8. TG/DTG curves of bramble leaves extract at 10 °C/min in a nitrogen atmosphere.

Figure S9. TG/DTG curves of yellow onion peels extract at 10 °C/min in a nitrogen atmosphere.

Figure S10. TG/DTG curves of grape marc extract at 10 °C/min in a nitrogen atmosphere.

Figure S11. TG/DTG curves of pomegranate peels extract at 10 °C/min in a nitrogen atmosphere.

MELT RHEOLOGY ANALYSIS OF PLA MATERIALS

Figure S12. Impact of processing on PLA materials: dynamic viscosity measured by melt rheology with frequency sweep tests performed at $T=200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $\dot{\gamma}=10\%$.

THERMOGRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS COUPLED WITH DIFFERENTIAL SCANNING CALORIMETRY OF PLA MATERIALS

Figure S13. TG curves of PLA materials monitored by TGA-DSC experiments under air.

Figure S14. DSC curves of PLA materials monitored by TGA-DSC experiments under air.

REFERENCES

- (1) Fischer, U. A.; Carle, R.; Kammerer, D. R. Identification and Quantification of Phenolic Compounds from Pomegranate (*Punica Granatum* L.) Peel, Mesocarp, Aril and Differently Produced Juices by HPLC-DAD–ESI/MSn. *Food Chemistry* **2011**, *127* (2), 807–821. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2010.12.156>.
- (2) Mena, P.; Calani, L.; Dall'Asta, C.; Galaverna, G.; García-Viguera, C.; Bruni, R.; Crozier, A.; Del Rio, D. Rapid and Comprehensive Evaluation of (Poly)Phenolic Compounds in Pomegranate (*Punica Granatum* L.) Juice by UHPLC-MSn. *Molecules* **2012**, *17* (12), 14821–14840. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules171214821>.
- (3) Bastos, K.; Dias, C.; Nascimento, Y.; da Silva, M.; Langassner, S.; Wessjohann, L.; Tavares, J. Identification of Phenolic Compounds from *Hancornia Speciosa* (Apocynaceae) Leaves by UHPLC Orbitrap-HRMS. *Molecules* **2017**, *22* (1), 143. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules22010143>.
- (4) Sanna, C.; Marengo, A.; Acquadro, S.; Caredda, A.; Lai, R.; Corona, A.; Tramontano, E.; Rubiolo, P.; Esposito, F. In Vitro Anti-HIV-1 Reverse Transcriptase and Integrase Properties of *Punica Granatum* L. Leaves, Bark, and Peel Extracts and Their Main Compounds. *Plants* **2021**, *10* (10), 2124. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants10102124>.
- (5) Maeda-Yamamoto, M.; Ema, K.; Monobe, M.; Tokuda, Y.; Tachibana, H. Epicatechin-3- O -(3"- O - Methyl)-Gallate Content in Various Tea Cultivars (*Camellia Sinensis* L.) and Its in Vitro Inhibitory Effect on Histamine Release. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **2012**, *60* (9), 2165–2170. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf204497b>.
- (6) Li, Q.; Jin, Y.; Jiang, R.; Xu, Y.; Zhang, Y.; Luo, Y.; Huang, J.; Wang, K.; Liu, Z. Dynamic Changes in the Metabolite Profile and Taste Characteristics of Fu Brick Tea during the Manufacturing Process. *Food Chemistry* **2021**, *344*, 128576. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2020.128576>.
- (7) Managa, M. G.; Sultanbawa, Y.; Sivakumar, D. Effects of Different Drying Methods on Untargeted Phenolic Metabolites, and Antioxidant Activity in Chinese Cabbage (*Brassica Rapa* L. Subsp. *Chinensis*) and Nightshade (*Solanum Retroflexum* Dun.). *Molecules* **2020**, *25* (6), 1326. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25061326>.